

GEOMAGNETIC ANOMALOUS SIGNAL ASSOCIATED WITH $M_w8.3$ COQUIMBO - CHILE EARTHQUAKE ON SEPTEMBER 16-th, 2015

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Introduction

In the last decade, the long-term real time ground-based geomagnetic observations, realized in the seismic active Vrancea zone (Stanica and Stanica, 2011, Stanica et al., 2018), together with supplementary studies regarding the M_w 9.0 Tohoku earthquake generated on March 11, 2011 (Stanica et al., 2015) and M_w 8.3 Chiapas earthquake on September 8, 2017 (Stănică and Stănică, 2019), have enlarged our knowledge about the inter-relations among the pre-seismic anomalous geomagnetic phenomena and the final stage of the earthquakes nucleation.

In this paper, we retrospectively analyzed the geomagnetic data collected on the interval 07 July–20 September 2015, via internet (www.intermagnet.com), at the observatories Easter Island (IMP) and Pilar (PIL) that are placed in Chile and Argentina, respectively (Fig. 1), to identify the possible relationship between the pre-seismic anomalous behaviour of the geomagnetic polarization parameter (BPOL) and $M_w8.3$ earthquake that occurred offshore Coquimbo (Chile) on September 16-th, 2015.

Fig. 1 Map with the $M_w8.3$ Coquimbo (Chile) earthquake and geomagnetic observatories (IMP and PIL) placements

Finally, the daily mean distribution of the polarization parameter BPOL and its standard deviation (STDEV) are performed in ULF range (0.001Hz-0083Hz) by using the FFT band-pass filter analysis. After analyzing the value of the parameter BPOL obtained at the both observatories, Pilar taken as reference one, we used a statistical analysis to identify on September 2, 2015 a pre-seismic geomagnetic signature related to Mw 8.3 Offshore Coquimbo earthquake and, the lead time was 14 days before the impending earthquake.

Methodology and results

In order to identify a pre-seismic geomagnetic signals related to Mw8.3earthquake it is necessarily to have information about:

- Polarization parameter (BPOL);
- Strain effect-related to the pre-seismic geomagnetic signal.

For a given 2D geoelectric structure, the vertical magnetic component $B_z(f)$ is a totally secondary field and it is produced essentially by the horizontal magnetic components $H(f) = \text{SQRT}[B_x^2(f) + B_y^2(f)]$. Consequently, the polarization parameter expressed as:

$$\text{BPOL}(f) = B_z(f) / \text{SQRT}[B_x^2(f) + B_y^2(f)], \quad (1)$$

should be time invariant in non-seismic condition and it becomes unstable before the onset of a seismic event (Stănică and Stănică, 2019).

As regards the distance at which the strain effect is able to generate a pre-seismic geomagnetic signal we used the following relation (Morgunov and Malzev, 2007):

$$R(\text{km}) = 10^{0.5M - 0.27}, \quad (2)$$

where: R is epicentral distance and M is earthquake magnitude.

As the strain effect of the Mw8.3 Coquimbo earthquake is felt at $R \approx 7600$ km, in this particular case, the distance between IMP and earthquake epicenter is about 3500 km and, 1000 km for PIL, respectively, so that the condition to identify a pre-seismic anomalous signals in the both observatories are fulfilled.

For data processing and analysis, the following steps have been used:

- a) a FFT band-pass filter analysis in the frequency range 0.001Hz -0.0083Hz has been performed on the BPOL time series for two successive time windows of 1024 samples, with 60% overlapping, on the entirely series of 1440 data points acquired each day at the both observatories;
- b) the new time series were used to calculate the daily mean value of BPOL and its standard deviation (STDEV) for IMP and PIL observatories, on the interval July 06 – September 22 2015, and the results are presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3;

Fig. 2 Daily mean distribution of the BPOL parameter and its STDEV obtained at IMP observatory; red star indicates Mw8.3earthquake, on September 16, 2015; ratio 8.3/20km is magnitude/hypocenter; red ellipse emphasizes the pre-seismic geomagnetic signal

Fig. 3 Daily mean distribution of the BPOL parameter and its STDEV obtained at PIL observatory; red star indicates Mw8.3earthquake on September 16, 2015; ratio 8.3/20km is magnitude/hypocenter; red ellipse emphasizes the pre-seismic geomagnetic signal

c) to assess the singularity of the pre-seismic anomalous signal, related to the M8.3 earthquake, a statistical analysis based on the standardized random variable equation (Stanica at.al., 2018; Stănică and Stănică, 2019) was applied and the final result presented as BPOL* distribution are shown in Fig. 4;

Fig. 4 Daily mean distribution of the BPOL* on August 1-September 20, 2015; red circle is Mw8.3earthquake; red ellipse is a pre-seismic anomalous signal on September 2, 2015; red dashed line (BPOL*=2) emphasizes the threshold for anomaly using STDEV

Conclusions

The proposed methodology concerning the distribution of the geomagnetic polarization parameters BPOL and BPOL*, last one being obtained by using a standardized random variable equation, provides adequate information to identify a peak level higher than 2 STDEV (red dashed line in Fig. 4), starting with September 2. The lead time was 14 days before the onset of the M8.3 Coquimbo (Chile) earthquake.

Finally, the above mentioned results could offer opportunities to develop new tools for early detection of the anomalous signals related to the major earthquakes. However, in terms of practical application the both BPOL and BPOL* parameters (Stănică and Stănică, 2019), as well as Bzn and Bzn* (Stanica at.al., 2018) are used in Romania by the Institute of Geodynamics of the Romanian Academy (Electromagnetism and Lithosphere Dynamics Department) for real time monitoring of the pre-seismic geomagnetic signals related to the Vrancea intermediate depth earthquakes.

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